

Electrochemical behaviour of cobalt(II) L-amino acids in aqueous dimethyl formamide, N-methylformamide and formamide media at dropping mercury electrode

B. S. Bairwa, Manu Gupta, Sarita Varshney, I. K. Sharma and P. S. Verma*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : psvermajaipur@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 22 May 2008, revised 26 October 2009, accepted 29 October 2009

Abstract : Polarographic technique has been used to evaluate the kinetic parameters and formation constants of cobalt(II) complexes with L-arginine, L-lysine, L-tryptophan, L-tyrosine, L-aspartic acid and L-glutamic acid at pH 8.40 ± 0.20 and at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1$) in aqueous dimethylformamide (DMF), N-methylformamide (NMF) and formamide mixture (v/v) at d.m.e. The reduction of all these complexes is found to be irreversible. The kinetic parameters (K_{th}^0 , αn , ξ) for these complexes were calculated using Meites-Israel method and its modification by Gaur and Bhargava. In all these cases a single reduction wave is obtained and i_d value decreases with increase in the percentage of solvent (20–60% v/v). Further it was observed that $E_{1/2}$ value shifted towards more negative side in all Co^{II} complexes in NMF medium possibly due to high dielectric constant and viscosity of the medium.

Keywords : NMF, DMF, DME, amino acid, cobalt(II).

Introduction

Amino acids are biologically active compounds and essential for human being and their reaction with metals have relevance to bio system. They have good chelating ability with metal ions and play an important role in biology and pharmacy. The reduction of Co^{II} complexes at d.m.e. in aqueous organic solvent has been studied and others have studied the mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} by different electroanalytical techniques¹. The present investigation deals with the study of electrode kinetics of the complexes of Co^{II} with L-amino acids in aqueous organic solvent systems (DMF, NMF and formamide) at varying composition (20–60% v/v).

Experimental

All solutions were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals in doubly distilled water. A conventional type manual polarograph was used for obtaining current voltage curves. The dropping mercury electrode used had the following characteristics : $m = 1.8$ mg/s and $t = 6.0$ s. Triton X-100 (0.001%) was used to suppress the polarographic maxima. Dissolved oxygen was removed by bubbling pu-

rified nitrogen gas through the solution, which had the same composition as that of the experimental matrix. NaClO₄ was used as base electrolyte. Solution containing (1.0 mM) of the metal ion, varying composition of DMF, NMF, formamide and water (v/v) were prepared at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1$) which was maintained using NaClO₄.

Results and discussion

In most cases a single reduction wave was obtained. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ and i_d vs concentration were linear passing through the origin indicating diffusion controlled reduction, where [i_d = diffusion current, h = height of mercury column]. Using eq. (1), the plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d,e}$, gives a straight line with slope 0.0591/ n volts.

$$E_{d,e} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0591}{n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (1)$$

The zero intercept on Y-axis gives the value of $E_{1/2}$. The values of slope indicated that the reduction of Co^{II} L-amino acid complexes in different percentage of DMF, NMF and formamide are irreversible. The kinetic parameters (K_{th}^0 , αn , ξ) were calculated from Meites-Is-

rael method² and also by further modified Gaur-Bhargava's method.

$$E_{d,e} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}}{1.128 \times D^{1/2}} - \frac{0.05690}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (2)$$

which may be written as

$$E_{d,e} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.05690}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (3)$$

with

$$E_{1/2} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}}{1.128 \times D^{1/2}} \quad (4)$$

where α is the transfer coefficient, n is the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step, K_{fh}^0 is the forward rate constant of the electron transfer at zero volts and D is the diffusion coefficient and other terms have their usual significances.

Thus, the value of αn was obtained from the slope of straight line corresponding to $E_{d,e}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$. The intercept of the same plot gives the value of $E_{1/2}$, which was used to calculate K_{fh}^0 after getting the value of D from the Ilkovic equation. Gaur-Bhargava have extended the Koutecky's treatment for irreversible wave since according to them the diffusion to the electrode surface (mercury drop) is spherical and not a linear one as was assumed by Meites and Israel.

The polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters for Co^{II} L-amino acid complexes are incorporated in Tables 1–3. The values of slopes are shown in Tables 1–3, which clearly indicate irreversible nature of reduction.

In all cases of our investigations a single reduction wave was obtained. The $E_{1/2}$ value is regularly shifted towards negative side and i_d value is decreased with increase in the percentage of DMF, NMF and formamide solvent media (20–60% v/v).

The half wave potential is marked by more cathodic shift as the percentage of dimethylformamide is increased from (20–60% v/v) in all the Co^{II} L-amino acid complexes.

The more cathodic behaviour of half wave potential

may be due to physical properties (viscosity, dielectric constant) of DMF. The slope of the plots and kinetic parameters were evaluated using Meites-Israel and Gaur-Bhargava's methods indicate irreversible reduction of the complexes. The K_{fh}^0 values indicate that the electrode process for the reduction of these complexes become some what more irreversible as the percentage of DMF is increased. The K_{fh}^0 values, however, go on decreasing with increase in the percentage of DMF.

The variation in polarographic characteristics of the complexes and the irreversibility of the electrode processes with change in solvent composition is obtained in DMF medium. This discrepancy is due to the formation of electric double layer³. Adsorption of polar solvent like dimethylformamide hinders the approach of electro active species to the d.m.e. Hence, the increase in the irreversibility of the electrode process with increase in percentage of DMF may be due to change in structure of double layer. The cathodic shift in $E_{1/2}$ and decrease in i_d value however, is not regular for Co^{II} L-arginine complex in 60% NMF (v/v) and the Co^{II} L-lysine complex in the 40% NMF (v/v). This discrepancy can be explained in terms of the chemical properties of depolarizer⁴, steric factor of the solvent molecule and viscosity of the medium. Change in solvation caused by changing the dielectric constant largely affects the values of the half wave potential. The dielectric constant values of DMF (37) and NMF (182.4) shows that the shift in $E_{1/2}$ is much higher in NMF than DMF medium. The results obtained, as shown in Tables 1 and 2, further confirm it.

The polarographic characteristics and kinetic parameters for Co^{II} L-amino acid complexes in formamide medium are incorporated in Table 3. In all cases a single reduction wave was obtained and the shift in $E_{1/2}$ potential is of regular order i.e. with increase in percentage of formamide (20–60% v/v), the $E_{1/2}$ is shifted towards negative side. i_d values decrease with increase in the percentage of the solvent. Further, it has been observed during the course of our investigation that shift in $E_{1/2}$ value is not regular in 40% Co^{II} L-arginine complex. This anomalous behaviour is due to the reasons as discussed for the complexes in NMF medium. Table 3 show the values of kinetic parameters (K_{fh}^0 , αn , ξ). The values of K_{fh}^0 indicate that irreversibility of the electrode reaction is in-

Note

Table 1. Kinetic parameters for Co^{II} complexes (1 mM) aqueous DMF mixtures of varying compositions ($\mu = 0.1$)

Ligand	Solvent (v/v, %)	i_d (μ A)	Slope (mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	αn	ξ	K_{fh}^0 (cm/s) Meites-Israel method	K_{fh}^0 (cm/s) Gaur- Bhargava's method
L-Arginine	0	8.10	82	1.164	3.35	0.72	0.33	6.005×10^{-15}	11.827×10^{-15}
	20	7.76	80	1.176	3.20	0.73	0.32	2.825×10^{-15}	5.567×10^{-15}
	40	7.65	80	1.194	3.16	0.73	0.32	1.762×10^{-15}	3.253×10^{-15}
	60	6.75	80	1.212	2.78	0.73	0.28	0.874×10^{-15}	1.655×10^{-15}
L-Aspartic acid	0	11.7	140	1.150	4.832	0.42	0.49	5.515×10^{-10}	11.424×10^{-10}
	20	10.687	112	1.156	4.401	0.52	0.45	11.993×10^{-12}	25.779×10^{-12}
	40	10.350	110	1.160	4.262	0.53	0.43	7.490×10^{-12}	15.855×10^{-12}
	60	9.785	100	1.204	4.031	0.59	0.41	4.608×10^{-13}	6.281×10^{-13}
L-Glutamic acid	0	9.90	108	1.164	4.088	0.54	0.41	4.655×10^{-12}	9.706×10^{-12}
	20	9.70	106	1.172	4.006	0.55	0.40	2.648×10^{-12}	5.552×10^{-12}
	40	8.66	100	1.194	3.576	0.59	0.36	3.393×10^{-12}	6.080×10^{-12}
	60	8.21	100	1.208	3.390	0.59	0.34	2.332×10^{-13}	4.607×10^{-13}
L-Lysine	0	11.25	80	1.192	4.70	0.73	0.46	2.714×10^{-15}	5.881×10^{-15}
	20	7.76	74	1.200	3.242	0.79	0.31	1.589×10^{-15}	3.068×10^{-15}
	40	6.75	70	1.230	2.820	0.84	0.276	8.019×10^{-18}	15.024×10^{-18}
	60	6.63	62	1.248	2.770	0.95	0.271	7.386×10^{-20}	13.839×10^{-20}
L-Tryptophan	0	7.537	90	1.174	3.167	0.65	0.304	5.675×10^{-14}	10.905×10^{-14}
	20	7.312	76	1.184	3.073	0.77	0.295	1.759×10^{-16}	3.321×10^{-16}
	40	6.975	74	1.194	2.931	0.79	0.282	5.227×10^{-16}	9.975×10^{-16}
	60	6.525	70	1.204	2.742	0.84	0.264	1.850×10^{-17}	3.460×10^{-17}
L-Tyrosine	0	8.100	114	1.146	3.354	0.51	0.337	1.971×10^{-12}	3.843×10^{-12}
	20	7.762	104	1.160	3.214	0.56	0.323	4.600×10^{-13}	8.935×10^{-13}
	40	7.650	100	1.176	3.168	0.59	0.318	3.185×10^{-13}	6.278×10^{-13}
	60	6.637	96	1.190	2.748	0.61	0.276	1.382×10^{-13}	2.599×10^{-13}

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for Co^{II} complexes (1 mM) aqueous NMF mixtures of varying compositions ($\mu = 0.1$)

Ligand	Solvent (v/v, %)	i_d (μ A)	Slope (mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	αn	ξ	K_{fh}^0 (cm/s) Meites-Israel method	K_{fh}^0 (cm/s) Gaur- Bhargava's method
L-Arginine	0	8.10	82	1.164	3.35	0.72	0.33	6.005×10^{-15}	11.827×10^{-15}
	20	11.362	124	1.220	4.692	0.47	0.476	2.573×10^{-16}	5.644×10^{-16}
	40	6.300	110	1.312	2.602	0.53	0.264	2.002×10^{-13}	3.731×10^{-13}
	60	8.325	104	1.254	3.438	0.56	0.348	2.682×10^{-13}	5.336×10^{-13}
L-Aspartic acid	0	9.90	108	1.164	4.088	0.54	0.41	4.65×10^{-12}	9.706×10^{-12}
	20	5.062	86	1.254	2.090	0.68	0.212	1.438×10^{-15}	2.574×10^{-15}
	40	8.6625	72	1.310	3.577	0.82	0.363	1.650×10^{-18}	3.319×10^{-18}
	60	7.0875	70	1.324	2.927	0.84	0.297	3.717×10^{-19}	7.106×10^{-19}
L-Glutamic acid	0	11.7	140	1.150	4.832	0.42	0.49	5.515×10^{-10}	11.424×10^{-10}
	20	2.868	128	1.422	1.184	0.46	0.120	1.294×10^{-10}	2.136×10^{-10}

Table-2 (contd.)

L-Lysine	40	2.925	170	1.430	1.208	0.34	0.122	4.824×10^{-12}	8.065×10^{-12}
	60	2.531	180	1.612	1.048	0.32	0.105	2.038×10^{-13}	3.401×10^{-13}
	0	11.25	80	1.192	4.7	0.73	0.46	2.714×10^{-15}	5.881×10^{-15}
	20	16.20	86	1.222	6.690	0.68	0.678	1.0736×10^{-14}	2.751×10^{-14}
L-Tryptophan	40	8.775	84	1.220	3.625	0.70	0.367	2.8617×10^{-15}	5.775×10^{-15}
	60	9.787	82	1.260	4.042	0.72	0.410	4.854×10^{-16}	10.12×10^{-16}
	0	7.537	90	1.174	3.167	0.65	0.304	5.675×10^{-14}	10.905×10^{-14}
	20	5.512	110	1.240	2.283	0.53	0.229	7.738×10^{-13}	14.06×10^{-13}
L-Tyrosine	40	6.637	92	1.302	2.756	0.64	0.275	2.760×10^{-15}	5.200×10^{-15}
	60	6.412	82	1.320	2.712	0.72	0.256	5.918×10^{-17}	11.06×10^{-17}
	0	8.100	114	1.146	3.354	0.51	0.337	1.971×10^{-12}	3.843×10^{-12}
	20	13.72	102	1.294	5.668	0.57	0.5752	1.227×10^{-13}	2.905×10^{-13}
	40	6.30	80	1.296	2.602	0.73	0.2640	7.556×10^{-17}	14.083×10^{-17}
	60	10.80	74	1.330	4.460	0.79	0.4526	3.875×10^{-18}	8.348×10^{-18}

Table 3. Kinetic parameters for Co^{II} complexes (1 mM) aqueous formamide mixtures of varying compositions ($\mu=0.1$)

Ligand	Solvent (v/v, %)	i_d (μA)	Slope (mV)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm^2 s^{-1})	αn	ξ	K_{fh}^0	K_{fh}^0
								Meites-Israel method	Gaur- Bhargava's method
L-Arginine	0	8.10	82	1.164	3.35	0.72	0.33	6.005×10^{-15}	11.827×10^{-15}
	20	9.000	88	1.178	3.727	0.67	0.375	2.7840×10^{-14}	5.6503×10^{-14}
	40	6.862	84	1.174	2.842	0.74	0.285	1.8547×10^{-15}	3.5153×10^{-15}
	60	5.625	92	1.204	2.329	0.64	0.234	2.7187×10^{-14}	4.9528×10^{-14}
L-Aspartic acid	0	11.7	140	1.150	4.832	0.42	0.49	5.515×10^{-10}	11.424×10^{-10}
	20	4.500	136	1.190	1.864	0.43	0.187	7.2019×10^{-11}	12.656×10^{-11}
	40	5.175	112	1.218	2.149	0.52	0.214	1.7111×10^{-12}	3.0699×10^{-12}
	60	4.725	104	1.250	1.951	0.56	0.198	1.6613×10^{-13}	2.9431×10^{-13}
L-Glutamic acid	0	9.90	108	1.164	4.088	0.54	0.41	4.655×10^{-12}	9.706×10^{-12}
	20	6.525	88	1.178	2.76	0.67	0.260	2.1957×10^{-14}	4.0876×10^{-14}
	40	5.512	116	1.200	2.324	0.50	0.221	5.8778×10^{-12}	10.603×10^{-12}
	60	6.075	98	1.244	2.545	0.60	0.247	5.4132×10^{-14}	9.9597×10^{-14}
L-Lysine	0	11.25	80	1.192	4.7	0.73	0.46	2.714×10^{-15}	5.881×10^{-15}
	20	7.875	104	1.172	3.31	0.56	0.3186	1.6265×10^{-12}	3.1612×10^{-12}
	40	6.975	98	1.198	2.922	0.60	0.2839	1.8199×10^{-13}	3.4441×10^{-13}
	60	6.300	100	1.202	2.632	0.59	0.2580	2.1503×10^{-13}	3.9890×10^{-13}
L-Tryptophan	0	7.537	90	1.174	3.167	0.65	0.304	5.675×10^{-14}	10.905×10^{-14}
	20	6.750	116	1.166	2.811	0.50	0.278	1.3291×10^{-11}	2.5039×10^{-11}
	40	6.412	104	1.200	2.637	0.56	0.261	7.1057×10^{-13}	1.3212×10^{-12}
	60	5.625	100	1.206	2.371	0.59	0.226	1.8168×10^{-13}	3.2890×10^{-13}
L-Tyrosine	0	8.100	114	1.146	3.354	0.51	0.337	1.971×10^{-12}	3.843×10^{-12}
	20	5.850	100	1.172	2.482	0.59	0.232	4.2327×10^{-13}	7.6984×10^{-13}
	40	6.637	116	1.208	2.807	0.50	0.265	6.1347×10^{-12}	11.443×10^{-12}
	60	6.075	94	1.248	2.561	0.62	0.244	1.8128×10^{-14}	3.3277×10^{-14}

creased with increase in the percentage of formamide. In the case of Co^{II} L-glutamic acid and Co^{II} L-tyrosine, K_{fh}^0 values are decreased in 40% formamide, while K_{fh}^0 values are increased at higher percentage (60% v/v) of formamide. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ value is compared for all six amino acids i.e. L-arginine, L-aspartic acid, L-glutamic acid, L-lysine, L-tryptophan and L-tyrosine in three aqueous organic solvent media i.e. DMF, NMF and formamide, it has been concluded that the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values is much higher in NMF medium than DMF and formamide. This is due to high dielectric constant of NMF (182.4) in comparison to DMF and formamide. If the limiting current of all the six L-amino acids in three organic solvent medium are compared then it can be concluded that limiting current is decreased more in formamide than in DMF and NMF, which may be assigned to the high viscosity of formamide (3.302).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank, the Head of Department of Chemistry for providing the laboratory facilities and U.G.C. Regional Office, Bhopal for providing Teacher Research Fellowship to Bhagwan Sahay Bairwa.

References

1. S. Varshney, PhD Thesis, Rajasthan University, 1991; R. S. Pandey and C. S. Pandey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 38; O. Buriez, E. Labbe and J. Perichon, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2006, **593**, 99; Mahmoud M. Mashaly, Tarek M. Ismail, Salah B. El-Maraghy and Hesham A. Habib, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2004, **57**, 1099.
2. L. Meites and Y. Israel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4903.
3. S. Mine, J. Jastrzebska and M. Brazostowska, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1961, **108**, 1160.
4. K. Schwabe, in "Advances in Polarography", ed. I. S. Longmuir, Pergamon Press, London, 1960, **3**, 911.

